

THE PLACE OF PRIMARY EDUCATION IN THE PIRLS INTERNATIONAL ASSESSMENT SYSTEM

Karimova Jahona

1st stage master of Tashkent State
Pedagogical University named after Nizami

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10408778>

Abstract. *This article discusses the work of the International Assessment Program PIRLS (Progress in International Reading And Literacy Study) to compare the work done and the results of the national education system in different countries around the world.*

Keywords: *PIRLS, PISA, TIMSS, international assessment program, the results of the research, national education system, reading literacy.*

This can solve the task of quickly providing the country's potential personnel team with representatives of the younger age group. It is important to understand the differences between the ages of the students admitted to the inner class. In the country, the age at which a child is admitted to school is determined by the national research coordinators. In addition, since the PIRLS study is a cross-sectional study, the program collects information about the policy of enrolling children in school at or after the specified age limit in the country and is a necessary factor in evaluating their learning outcomes.

Research shows that sending children to school late does not have a positive effect on their academic performance or emotional state, so this procedure is considered ineffective. Therefore, in many participating countries, children who are admitted late, especially in the primary grades, are automatically admitted to the upper grades. Longer years of schooling allow students to acquire more knowledge and become literate young people with higher levels of education.

In the PIRLS 2016 international study, in most countries, the age of admission to primary school is about 6 years, and the age of completion of compulsory education is about 16 years. Curriculum is organized at the state, district, school, or other level, based on the knowledge, skills, and attitudes that students should be taught, acquired, or mastered by educational standards. It is planned to provide education to students.

Public policies and curricula adopted to help students acquire reading literacy include standards or standardized tests aimed at developing reading skills. Strategies and Guidelines for Developing Students' Reading Comprehension Skills At a time when Uzbekistan is rapidly developing on the path of innovative development, comprehensive support of creativity and intellectual abilities of young people who are the successors of our future in the field of education, formation of their knowledge, skills and qualifications and advanced foreign it is important to perfect the assessment system based on experiences, international criteria and requirements, to study international experiences, to conduct a comprehensive comparative analysis of the existing system, to closely cooperate with relevant international and foreign organizations and scientific research institutions. In this regard, the establishment of cooperation with the International Association for the Evaluation of Educational Achievement (IEA-International Association for the Evaluation of Educational Achievement) can be cited as an example.

For more than 60 years, the IEA has been a leading organization in the field of comparative education. This organization conducts large-scale research in the field of education in order to

study the influence of state policy and practice in the education system. In addition, in the Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated April 29, 2019 "On approval of the concept of development of the public education system of the Republic of Uzbekistan until 2030" No. PF-5712, the PISA international program by 2030 ranking among the first 30 advanced countries of the world and people. Based on the organization of international studies in the field of education quality assessment in the education system, the tasks of creating a national system of education quality assessment aimed at assessing the literacy level of students in reading, mathematics and natural sciences have been defined.

Also, within the framework of the concept, taking into account the development of students' critical and creative thinking, independent search for information, analytical competencies and skills, introducing general education programs and new state education standards that meet the requirements of the modern innovative economy. , continuous participation in international PISA, TIMSS, PIRLS and other programs is provided for the assessment of students' knowledge level. A successful participation in the PIRLS research has a special place in the implementation of these tasks.

Progress in International Reading and Literacy Study (PIRLS) is a criterion for evaluating the level of reading and comprehension of primary 4th graders, that is, the reading comprehension skills of primary graders. is a major international assessment program that enables international comparisons of progress data and informs public education policy to improve learning and teaching. The PIRLS study survey collects information about public support for children's early school entry and the process of children's inclusion in preschool education. In the PIRLS 2016 study, almost all participating countries have pre-school programs for children aged 3 or older, and a number of countries have also included pre-school programs for children under 3 years of age.

In addition, EU participating countries have made it mandatory for children to be enrolled in pre-school education. It is known that the impact of the child's further education and life depends on the quality of the pre-school education process. The earlier the child is involved in the continuous education environment, the more significant progress will be made in the next stages, that is, time will be saved. is to make changes to the existing reading comprehension strategy and to transform the students into fast and fluent readers. Another aspect of the ePIRLS study, which assesses students' reading comprehension of electronic information materials, concerns the extent to which a country's curriculum can support students' reading comprehension of electronic materials and new format resources.

As noted in the PIRLS 2016 Encyclopedia, some countries have standards that help teach students in elementary schools strategies for reading and understanding electronic texts, such as how to interact with and locate online materials. making changes to programs and assignments. In each assessment cycle, PIRLS National Research Coordinators provide information on educational research in their countries through the PIRLS Encyclopedia. As an example, it is appropriate to say that in the study to be conducted in 2021, it is planned to present assignments in digital format to students for the first time.

Along with the transition to a digital format, changes such as computer-based assessment of ePIRLS online learning administered in a web environment are also envisaged. At the same time, several samples of PIRLS research tasks, i.e. texts and questions, and their evaluation criteria are presented. In conclusion, the results of researches within the PIRLS international assessment

program are regularly updated, which makes it possible to achieve more efficiency by applying these results in school education. It is necessary to create a unique national system based on the analysis of the results obtained and shown by the national research coordinators. The relevance of observational and experimental studies is important in this.

REFERENCES

1. Evaluation of reading literacy of elementary school students in international studies. (Methodical manual for primary school teachers, methodologists and industry experts) Chief editorial office of "Sharq" publishing-printing joint-stock company. Tashkent-2019.
2. Assessment of students' mathematical literacy in international studies. (Methodological manual for teachers of mathematics, methodologists and experts in the field) Chief editorial office of "Sharq" publishing-printing joint-stock company. Tashkent-2019.
3. Assess the reading literacy of students in international studies (methodical guide for teachers of mother tongue and literature, methodologists and specialists) "Sharq" publishing-printing joint-stock company Chief editor. Tashkent - 2019.
4. Notten, N., & Kraaykamp, G. Parental media socialization and educational attainment: Resource or disadvantage Research in Social Stratification and Mobility, (2010) , 453–464.
5. Baker, L., & Scher, D. Beginning readers' motivation for reading in relation to parental beliefs and home reading experiences. Reading Psychology, (2002), 239– 269.
6. Musaxonovna, K. L. General secondary schools requirements for the introduction of informed educational resources for the development of natural sciences. ACADEMICIA: An International Multidisciplinary Research Journal, (2022), 855- 860.